

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Resin-injection repair of barely visible impact damage on carbon fibre composite laminates

Wei Liang Lai, Hamid Saeedipour and Kheng Lim Goh

Newcastle Research & Innovation Institute, Singapore (NewRIIS)

Newcastle University in Singapore (NUIS)

Republic Polytechnic, Singapore

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Composite application

(Image from Boeing)

Impact damage on radome
(Image from Lufthansa Technik)

BMW 7's hybrid roof frame construction
(Image from SGL Group)

Impact damage on sills
(Image from Reverie Ltd)

Carbon bike and wheels

Impact damage on fork
(Image from Rein4ced)

Damage in CFRP laminates

Low velocity impact, Barely visible impact damage

Quasi-static indentation

Resin injection method for composite repair

Low velocity impact, Barely visible impact damage

- **Basic principles**

- Resin-injection hole are drilled at the centre of impact area.
- Vent holes are drilled at the periphery of the delamination.
- Low-viscosity resin is injected in the resin-injection hole until it flows out from the vent hole.

- **Limitations**

- Drilling holes result in fibre and matrix removal.
- Moisture removal in the damaged area is difficult to achieve.
- Difficult to achieve complete resin infiltration to the full crack network.

- **Solutions ?**

(a) Creation of a resin injection hole and vent holes at the BVID site.

(b) Injection of resin into the BVID site.

Strategy for effective resin injection repair

Objectives	Possible solutions
Minimize effects of vent hole	Epoxy resin with good mechanical properties
	Optimal number of vent holes
Removal of moisture and debris	Low pressure environment
Enhanced resin properties	Epoxy resin with good mechanical and physical properties
Enhanced resin infiltration	Low viscous epoxy resin (Flowability)
	Epoxy resin with high surface energy relative to CFRP

Epoxy resin

Basic principles

- Low molecular weight pre-polymer containing more than one epoxide group.
- Properties are dependent on the specific combination of epoxy resins and curing agents.
- Good bonding to many substrates; Good heat and chemical resistances; Good mechanical properties

Limitation

- Cracks: High exotherm during cure, resin rich areas, poor mixing.
- Porosity and Voids: Entrapped air during mixing.
- Delamination and Disbond: Adhesion failure (Poor surface preparation)
- Poor Cure: Poor mixing, poor temperature control.

Solutions?

F.L. Jin, X. Li, S.J. Park, Synthesis and application of epoxy resins: A review, J. Ind. Eng. Chem. 29 (2015) 1–11.
R. Stewart, M. Parmar, G. Bishop, Repair and Inspection of Composites: Review Report, Leicestershire, UK, 1999.

Nanoparticle reinforced in matrix

H. Ismail, P. Pasbakhsh, M.N. Ahmad Fauzi, A. Abu Bakar, The effect of halloysite nanotubes as a novel nanofiller on curing behaviour, mechanical and microstructural properties of ethylene propylene diene monomer (EPDM) nanocomposites, Polym. - Plast. Technol. Eng. 48 (2009) 313–323.

Methods for investigation of composite repair

Vent Holes and Repair efficiency

$$\text{Repair efficiency} = \frac{F_{\text{Repair}} - F_{\text{Damaged}}}{F_{\text{Pristine}} - F_{\text{Damaged}}}$$

Number of vent hole	Vent hole diameter, mm	Resin-injection hole diameter, mm	Laminate Thickness, mm	Matrix	Impact energy, J	Repair efficiency, %	Significance of features contributing to the repair efficiency
4	1	3.5	2.45	Rutapox CY160N/SL Epoxy	20 (dynamic)	97 ^{avg}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thin laminates; through thickness damage readily accessible by resin Moderately high impact energy, inducing well-connected, large internal crack network Large injection hole that could deliver an adequate amount of resin into the crack
4	1	1	6.4	DREp epoxy	10 (static)	85-105 ^{ind}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thick laminates; through thickness damage may not be readily accessible by resin Low impact energy, inducing small internal cracks that were not well-connected Small injection hole leading to inadequate amount of resin delivered, insufficient to infiltrate all the cracks due to poor connectivity
4	1	1	4	RTM6 epoxy	16 (dynamic)	85-110 ^{ind}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderately thick laminates; through thickness damage may not be readily accessible by resin Drop tests yielded inconsistency in the force inflicted on the specimen Moderately high impact energy, inducing pockets of small internal cracks that may not be sufficiently well-connected Small injection hole, leading to inadequate amount of resin delivered, and this may be insufficient to infiltrate all the cracks
4	1	1	4	Loctite 406 epoxy	10 (dynamic)	53-67 ^{ind}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderately thick laminates, through thickness damage may not be readily accessible by resin Drop tests yielded inconsistency in the force inflicted on the specimen A low impact energy, inducing pockets of small internal cracks that were not well-connected Higher resin viscosity (Loctite 406 contained rubber particles, intended for toughening the resin), resulting in reduced flow of resin into all cracks Small injection hole, leading to inadequate infiltration of the resin into the cracks, also partly due to poor connectivity
4	1	1	4	Loctite 435 epoxy	10 (dynamic)	67-101 ^{ind}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lower resin viscosity (Loctite 435 did not contain rubber particles)
6	3.175	3.175	3	BECy (EX1510/B) bismaleimide	21 (dynamic)	99-110 ^{ind}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thin laminates; through thickness damage readily accessible by resin Moderately high impact energy, inducing a well-connected internal crack network Large injection hole that could deliver an adequate amount of resin into the crack More (and larger) vent holes, may enable more effective air extraction from cracks, reducing potential back-flow of resin, increasing the infiltration of resin into the well-connected cracks
6	3.175	3.175	4	BECy (EX1510/B) bismaleimide	30 (static)	47-126 ^{ind}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderately thick laminates; through thickness damage may not be readily accessible by resin High impact energy, inducing much larger and more extensive internal cracks, with varied degree of connectivity
6	3.175	3.175	4	Araldite GY257 epoxy	24 (dynamic)	91 ^{ind}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderately thick laminates; through thickness damage may not be readily accessible by resin Moderately high impact energy, inducing large and extensive internal cracks, that were somewhat well-connected Large injection hole that could deliver an adequate amount of resin into the crack More (and larger) vent holes, may enable more effective air extraction from cracks, reducing potential back-flow of resin, increasing the infiltration of resin into the well-connected cracks

Holes in specimens

24-ply CFRP laminates, Damaged factor, Morphology

Vent holes (Mechanical properties)

24-ply CFRP laminates, damaged, and in-plane compression test

In-plane compression test
Test method comply to ASTM D7137 for compressive residual strength properties of damaged polymer matrix composite plates.

- Fracture strength and toughness were significantly reduced after BVID.
- Vent holes does not lead to drastic decrease in fracture strength and toughness.
- Mean value of fracture strength and toughness shows reduction when vent holes were introduced.

Setup of resin-injection procedure

Operation of VARID

Repair efficiency using VARID

16-ply CFRP laminates, damaged, and repair using DGEBA resin, 4vent holes

- BVID results to reduction of strength and toughness.
- Resin-injection method use to repair the BVID in CFRP could restore the strength and toughness.
- Repaired specimens show large variability than the pristine specimen (Repeatability issue of repair?)

In-plane compression test

Ultrasound
C-scan image

Damaged

Repaired

Nanocomposite resins

Epoxy, nanoparticles, and mechanical properties

Tensile

ASTM D638

- NF100 shows the highest mean σ_u , while the E/1MWCNT has the lowest mean σ_u .
- Strain, U_E and U_F decreases when particles concentration increase.
- NF100 has the highest mean E_U , while the E/1HNT has the lowest mean E_U .

Lap Shear

ASTM D5868

- Result shows that there are no significant different in τ_u among the different type of epoxy tested.
- Neat epoxy shows the highest mean τ_u , while the E/3HNT shows the lowest τ_u .

Nanocomposite resins

Epoxy, nanoparticles, contact angle and viscosity

Contact Angle

ASTM D7334

M.K. Chaudhury, Interfacial interaction between low energy surfaces., Mater. Sci. Eng. R16 (1996) 97–159.

Viscosity

- Results derived using an Anton-Paar MCR302 rheometer.
- Viscosity increases when the particle concentration increase.
- Shear thinning occurs when the shear rate increases.
- Viscosity of neat epoxy and epoxy with 1%, 3% and 5% of HNTs show no significant differences.
- E/1%MWCNT and E/1%MWCNT with Triton X-100 is not suitable for resin injection method (High viscous).

Nanocomposite resins

Epoxy, nanoparticles, and thermal properties

- The experiment was conducted following a protocol in ASTM E2250.
- Initial decomposition temperature of the epoxy starts at 320°C.
- Final decomposition temperature of the epoxy at 420°C.
- Char residue of epoxy with higher nanoparticles concentration increased in comparison to the neat epoxy.
- Increasing of the char residue enhances the thermal stability of the nanocomposites as the formation of char hinders the diffusion of the volatile decomposition products.

H. Ismail, P. Pasbakhsh, M.N.A. Fauzi, A. Abu Bakar, Morphological, thermal and tensile properties of halloysite nanotubes filled ethylene propylene diene monomer (EPDM) nanocomposites, Polym. Test. 27 (2008) 841–850.

Conclusion

- **The fewer the vent holes the better** - Different mechanical properties of **BVID** laminate have different sensitivity to number of **vent holes**.
- **Nanocomposite resins with good mechanical and physical properties** - (1) Epoxy/HNT, (2) Epoxy/CNT (NanoForce-100, Nano-Tech SpA, Italy)
- **Repair efficiency using nanocomposite resin** - Higher mechanical properties can be achieved after repairing BVID laminates using nanocomposite resin (NanoForce-100), but importantly, with small variability (repeatable).

Acknowledgement

Advanced Composites Research Group

Kheng Lim Goh (Newcastle University in Singapore)

Hamid Saeedipour (Republic Polytechnic, Singapore)

Eugene Wong (Newcastle University in Singapore)

Geoff Gibson (Newcastle University, UK)

Collaborators

Pooria Pasbakhsh (Monash University Malaysia)

Edmund Liew (Singapore Institute of Technology)

Fundings

Technology Innovation Funds, Ministry of Education, Singapore

Republic Polytechnic Aerospace Hub

Thank you for your attention